

Survey Questionnaire in ‘Methodologies in the Identification, Analysis, and Measurement of Visual Pollution: The Case Study of Intramuros’

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Introduction

This document separately presents the survey questionnaire used for the Direct Method of Landscape Evaluation in SD Barroga’s research entitled Methodologies in the Identification, Analysis, and Measurement of Visual Pollution: The Case Study of Intramuros (2020).

The survey questionnaire was formulated with the goal of quantifying a certain degree of the personal taste variable suggested by Berlyne’s Theory of Aesthetic. The first part of the survey is aimed to gather demographic information of the respondent such as age, place of residence at the time of the survey, and if they have visited Intramuros at least once. Respondents that have visited Intramuros were required to describe Intramuros with one word.

The second part was designed to answer the following questions:

1. Which among the selected viewpoints were perceived to be beautiful?
2. Which were considered ugly?
3. Which were considered an interesting landscape?
4. Which were considered boring?
5. Which represents the character of Intramuros?

According to de la Fuente, G., Atauri, J., and de Lucio, J (1999), exhaustion of the respondent should be avoided since it may produce biased results. The questions per landscape code/ 360 panorama photo extracted from Google Maps were limited to three listed below:

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering No would mean it is ugly)
2. Is the landscape interesting? (Answering No would mean it is boring)
3. Is it taken in the district of Intramuros?

Questions 1 and 2 contains pair descriptors adopted from the study “Meaning and Form in Community Perception of Town Character” by Green (1999). Question 3 was aimed to determine whether the photo fits the respondent’s image of Intramuros.

The goal of the last part of the survey was to let the respondents identify which elements contributed to a beautiful and an ugly landscape.

Survey Guide

I. Personal Information

1. Age: ____
2. Place of Residence: ____
3. Years of Stay in Current Residence: ____
4. Have you been to the Walled City of Intramuros? Yes No
5. If yes, describe how Intramuros looks and feels like. _____

II. Visual Quality Assessment

Landscape Photo 1

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 2

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 3

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 4

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 5

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 6

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 7

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 8

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 9

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 10

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 11

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 12

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 13

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 14

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 15

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 16

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 17

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 18

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 19

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 20

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 21

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

Landscape Photo 22

1. Is the landscape in the photo beautiful? (Answering “No” would mean it is ugly.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is beautiful.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is ugly.
2. Is the landscape in the photo interesting? (Answering “No” would mean it is boring.)	<input type="radio"/> Yes, it is interesting.	<input type="radio"/> No, it is boring.
3. Do you think the photo is taken in Intramuros?	<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input type="radio"/> No

III. Description

1. Please describe the beautiful landscapes you remember. _____
2. Please describe the landscapes you remember as ugly. _____

References

Barroga, S.D. (2020). *Methodologies in the Identification, Analysis, and Measurement of Visual Pollution: The Case Study of Intramuros*. Quezon City: University of the Philippines Diliman.

de la Fuente de Val, G., Atauri, J., & de Lucio, J. (2005). Relationship between landscape visual attributes and spatial indices: A test study in Mediterranean-climate landscapes. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, Vol. 77, 393-407.

Green, R. (1999). Meaning and form in community perception of town character. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Vol. 19, 311-329.